

Rabindranath Tagore's Chandalika as a Cognitive Play

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Rabindranath Tagore is a renowned poet, musician and an artist. He was a Bengalian and English writer. In 1913 he won Nobel Prize for this notable work Gitanjali. His compositions were selected as National Anthem for two nations, India and Bangladesh. He also wrote many other short stories and novels. Chandalika is the play by Tagore which brings out ideas of upliftment of lower class people without degrading high class people.

Chandalika means the forbidden girl. Tagore always raised his voice against the maliciousness done by man to fellow men through the segmentation of caste and community. He always pleaded for the the perception that it is the Supreme Power who is Sporting in the world in so many forms like elegant and hideous. That it is our immunity his children to participate and adore that sport.

Tagore has deliberately given the heroine the name of Prakriti. The term means native, nature with all its elevated possibilities and the rigid actuality. Prakriti is convicted by the society Atul live a creep because of the the background of her birth. She has not known any e affection except that of her mother. When Buddhist monk Ananda asks the chandalika girl Prakriti to pour drinking water into his cupped hands. Prakriti who is basically pure readily accept the connotation of this small art. Her awareness suddenly blooms like the lotus in the rising Sun and she became profoundly awake of the honor to which she is characterized as a human being. Thus Prakriti and Ananda stand at the two Extreme levels of a psychological ratio. The two are brought together near the well of life.

A sense of her personality expanding into egoism and self conceit in Prakriti's mind started working. She wants the Buddhist Bhikshu in her arms and she is insisting her mother to use her eerie skills to bring the Bhikshu to her. The Bhikshu's words of advice to her had given her a sense of het own existence as a human being. Later she has began to think herself an significant person having the right to fall in love and having the right to await for an encouraging acknowledgment to her love. In this belief Prakriti is going too far in the direction of egoism and self conceit. Herself gas become more essential in her eyes.

The situation is aggravated when one day Ananda again happens to pass the same well, yet this time he is in an association of a group of other Buddhist monks, he does not even look in the direction of the well where a chandal girl quashed his thirstiness. Noticing Ananda's complete negligence to her and to the well. She thought that Ananda had forgotten her existence. She now strengthens her intentions to conquer Ananda and fore sin through the power of her mother. The mother who is is helpless to bare her daughters adversity agrees to workout her magic spells.

After fifteen days of continuous chanting the magic spell started working. Prakriti can see the passion for sensual desire, which the Buddhist monk is fighting hard against his own sensual pleasure for thr Chandal girl who had given him water to quench his thirst. In response to the spells, Ananda has already being travelling through the forest over The Hills in direction to Prakriti's house. Prakriti asks her mother to drive the Buddhist monk come to her and ask for water once again. This time she would give him water from the ocean of a heart.

She finds that the Buddhist monk has come very close to her house and feels happy to see him. She also sees the Buddhist monk's struggle to overcome his allurements towards the chandal girl. By seeing the struggle of her beloved she she asks her mother to stop the chanting. The Bhikshu against of his own misery pardons and blesses Prakriti at the end. She also realizes the fact that love for a person cannot be forced by anyone. She apologized for her guilt and changed her perception.

Thus play emphasizes Tagore's ideas that the helpless and the distressed have to be given a helping hand to come up in the communal and ethical scope. This cannot be attained by bringing the high class to the base level.